

Role of Chloride in the Ruthenium(III) catalysed Oxidation of Amino Acids by Chloramine-T in Aqueous Perchloric Acid Medium

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Manuscript received 3 July 1989, revised 29 January 1990, accepted 7 May 1990

Kinetics of Ru^{III} catalysed oxidations of several amino acids (AA) (glycine, alanine, valine, leucine, phenylalanine and serine) by chloramine-T in the presence of chloride ion have been studied in aqueous perchloric acid medium. All the amino acids except glycine show second order kinetics in [oxidant], fractional order each in [AA], [Ru^{III}] and [Cl⁻], and inverse fractional order in [H⁺], as compared to the second order dependences in [oxidant], first order in [AA], fractional order in [Cl⁻] and inverse first order in [H⁺], generally observed for uncatalysed oxidations. Variations in ionic strength of the medium or the addition of the reduced product of the oxidant had no significant effect on the rates of reactions. Decrease in dielectric constant of the medium by changing the solvent composition with methanol decreased the rate in all the cases. Two-pathway mechanisms have been considered to account for the observed kinetic and other effects. The rate controlling steps have been identified and co-efficients of these steps are calculated at different temperatures by varying [AA] at each temperature. The latter constants have been used to calculate the activation parameters associated with the rate-limiting steps. The rate constants are also predicted from the rate laws as [AA], [Ru^{III}] and [H⁺] are varied. The predicted values are in good agreement with the experimental constants, thus providing support to the suggested mechanisms.

OXIDATIVE decarboxylation of amino acids is of importance both from a pure chemical point of view and from the point of view of its bearing on the mechanism of amino acid metabolism. The free amino acids take part in numerous metabolic reactions. Specific metabolic role of amino acids include the biosynthesis of polypeptides and proteins and synthesis of nucleotides etc.

Mechanism of analogous non-enzymatic chemical processes of oxidative decarboxylation of amino acids is not well-established and it is a potential area for intensive experimentation. In an attempt to explain the course of the positive halogen reactions under varying conditions of acidity and chloride concentrations, we have recently studied the kinetics of oxidations of amino acids by chloramine-T^{1,2}. Metallic ions play a significant role in the oxidative decarboxylation of amino acids³. Hence in the present investigations, the role of Ru^{III} catalysis in the oxidative decarboxylation of amino acids by chloramine-T has been studied in aqueous perchloric acid under varying conditions.

Experimental

An aqueous stock solution (0.1 mol dm⁻³) of chloramine-T (CAT) (Fluka, AG) was standardised by iodometric method. Chromatographically pure glycine (Gly), L-alanine (Ala), L-valine (Val), L-leucine (Leu), L-phenylalanine (Phe) and L-serine (Ser) (Sisco Research Laboratories) were used. Aqueous stock solutions of amino acids (0.1 mol dm⁻³)

were prepared and standardised. All other reagents used were of accepted grades of purity. Ionic strength of the medium was kept at a high value (0.30 mol dm⁻³) employing concentrated aqueous solution of sodium perchlorate.

Kinetic measurements: The kinetic runs were made in glass-stoppered pyrex boiling tubes under pseudo-first order conditions with [amino acids] \gg [CAT] (at least by 5–10 times). The reactions were initiated by the rapid addition of requisite amounts of oxidant solution (0.0005–0.005 mol dm⁻³), pre-equilibrated at a desired temperature, to mixtures containing required amounts of amino acid (0.005–0.10 mol dm⁻³), perchloric acid (0.01–0.05 mol dm⁻³), sodium chloride (0.01–0.20 mol dm⁻³), RuCl₃ (0.4 × 10⁻⁴–1.6 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³) solutions and water, thermostated at the same temperature. The progress of the reactions was monitored for at least two half-lives by iodometric estimation of unreacted oxidant at regular intervals of time. The pseudo-first order rate constants (*k*_{obs}) were computed by the graphical methods and the values were reproducible within ±3% error.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: The stoichiometry of CAT-amino acid (AA) oxidations was determined in aqueous perchloric acid (0.01–0.05 mol dm⁻³), in the presence of NaCl (0.01–0.20 mol dm⁻³) and RuCl₃ (0.0–1.2 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³), by equilibrating varying ratios of [CAT]₀ to [AA]₀ at 303 K for different time intervals. Nitrite was identified as the major product by standard tests⁴ and recording the spectra of the reaction

TABLE 1—VALUES OF k_{obs} FOR Ru^{III} CATALYSED OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS BY CHLORAMINE-T IN AQUEOUS PERCHLORIC ACID MEDIUM IN PRESENCE OF CHLORIDE ION AT 303 K

[CAT] ₀ × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[AA] ₀ × 10 ² mol dm ⁻³	[HClO ₄] × 10 ² mol dm ⁻³	[Cl ⁻] × 10 mol dm ⁻³	[RuCl ₃] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	k_{obs} × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	k_{obs} (× 10 dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				
						Ala	Val	Leu	Phe	Ser
Effect of varying [CAT] ₀						Gly				
0.5	2.0	3.0	1.0	4.0	6.3	5.3	8.5	9.7	6.5	7.3
1.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	4.0	6.3	5.3	8.6	9.8	6.6	7.4
2.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	4.0	6.3	5.3	8.6	9.8	6.6	7.3
4.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	4.0	6.3	5.3	8.6	9.8	6.6	7.4
Effect of varying [AA] ₀										
1.0	1.0	3.0	1.0	4.0	4.4	3.8	5.9	6.0	4.8	5.6
1.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	4.0	6.3	5.3	8.6	9.8	6.6	7.4
1.0	5.0	3.0	1.0	4.0	9.3	10.8	17.4	20.0	12.4	12.8
1.0	10.0	3.0	1.0	4.0	13.1	19.2	31.3	37.8	21.8	20.6
Effect of varying [HClO ₄]										
1.0	2.0	1.0	1.0	4.0	9.1	13.8	19.0	23.8	19.3	18.2
1.0	2.0	2.0	1.0	4.0	7.7	7.6	11.3	14.4	10.0	9.8
1.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	4.0	6.3	5.3	8.6	9.8	6.6	7.4
1.0	2.0	5.0	1.0	4.0	5.2	3.9	6.0	6.4	4.4	4.6
Effect of varying [Cl ⁻]										
1.0	2.0	3.0	0.2	4.0	3.3	3.8	4.9	5.2	4.1	4.4
1.0	2.0	3.0	0.5	4.0	4.4	4.4	6.5	7.3	4.8	6.0
1.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	4.0	6.3	5.3	8.6	9.8	6.6	7.4
1.0	2.0	3.0	2.0	4.0	7.9	6.9	10.5	11.2	7.4	9.5
Effect of varying [RuCl ₃]										
1.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	4.0	6.3	5.3	8.6	9.8	6.6	7.4
1.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	8.0	7.2	6.9	11.2	11.5	7.8	8.9
1.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	12.0	8.1	7.6	12.9	12.9	8.7	10.2
1.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	16.0	8.9	8.5	15.5	14.1	9.6	11.2

mixture. The other product was aldehyde. The toluene-*p*-sulphonamide (TSA), the reduced product of the oxidant was detected by paper chromatography with benzyl alcohol saturated with water as the solvent and 0.5% vanillin in 1% HCl solution in ether as the spray reagent. The observed stoichiometry may be represented by equation (1) or (2).

where, Ar = CH₃C₆H₄, R = H(Gly), CH₃(Ala), (CH₃)₂CH(Val), (CH₃)₂CHCH₂(Leu), C₆H₅CH₂(Phe), HOH₂C(Ser).

Results and Discussion

Kinetics of Ru^{III} catalysed oxidation of several amino acids in the presence of chloride ion by CAT have been studied in aqueous perchloric acid medium under varying conditions. The results are shown in Tables 1–4 and Figs. 1–5. At constant [HClO₄] (0.03 mol dm⁻³), [Cl⁻], [Ru^{III}] and [AA]₀, plots of 1/[CAT] vs time were linear at least upto 75% completion of reaction, except for Gly, where plots of log [CAT]₀/[CAT] vs time were linear. Pseudo-second order and pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) computed from the respective plots were insensitive to the variations in [CAT]₀

(Table 1) establishing first order kinetics in [CAT] for Gly and second order in [CAT] for all other amino acids. At fixed [CAT]₀, [AA]₀, [Cl⁻] and [Ru^{III}], the rates decreased with increase in [HClO₄] (Table 1) and the plots of log k_{obs} vs log [HClO₄]

 TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING IONIC STRENGTH (I) AND DIELECTRIC CONSTANT OF MEDIUM AND ADDITION OF THE REDUCED PRODUCT OF OXIDANT (TSA) ON Ru^{III} CATALYSED OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS BY CHLORAMINE-T IN AQUEOUS PERCHLORIC ACID MEDIUM IN PRESENCE OF CHLORIDE ION AT 303 K

I mol dm ⁻³	k_{obs} × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹ Gly	k_{obs} (× 10 dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				
		Ala	Val	Leu	Phe	Ser
0.1	6.3	5.3	8.6	9.6	6.6	7.3
0.3	6.4	5.3	8.6	9.8	6.6	7.4
0.4	6.4	5.4	8.5	9.9	6.6	7.3
0.5	6.3	5.4	8.5	9.8	6.5	7.4
% MeOH						
10	3.8	4.0	7.2	5.5	5.1	7.3
20	2.6	3.0	6.3	3.6	4.2	5.0
30	1.2	2.2	5.2	2.6	3.2	4.2
40	1.1	1.2	4.2	1.2	2.5	2.9
[TSA] (× 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³)						
1.0	6.3	5.3	8.6	9.6	6.6	7.3
2.0	6.3	5.3	8.6	9.9	6.5	7.8
3.0	6.4	5.4	8.5	9.8	6.6	7.4
5.0	6.3	5.3	8.4	9.9	6.4	7.6

10³[CAT]₀ = 50 [AA]₀ = 33.33, [HClO₄] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³,
10³[Ru^{III}] = 4.0 mol dm⁻³, [Cl⁻] = 0.10 mol dm⁻³,
I = 0.30 mol dm⁻³ (except during its variation).

TABLE 3—KINETIC DATA FOR Ru^{III} CATALYSED OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS BY CHLORAMINE-T BOTH IN PRESENCE AND ABSENCE OF CHLORIDE ION IN COMPARISON WITH THOSE FOR UNCATALYSED OXIDATIONS

Orders observed in	Gly	Ala	Val	Leu	Phe	Ser
Ru ^{III} catalysed oxidations in the presence of Cl ⁻						
[CAT]	1.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0
[AA]	0.44	0.69	0.80	0.75	0.67	0.60
[H ⁺]	-0.31	-0.77	-0.70	-0.79	-0.75	-0.65
[Cl ⁻]	0.26	0.26	0.30	0.35	0.30	0.32
[Ru ^{III}]	0.30	0.33	0.40	0.30	0.26	0.30
Uncatalysed oxidations in the presence of Cl ⁻						
[CAT]	1.0	2.0	2.0	—	2.0	—
[AA]	0.59	1.0	1.0	—	1.0	—
[H ⁺]	-0.62	-1.0	-1.0	—	-1.0	—
[Cl ⁻]	0.22	0.4	0.64	—	0.3	—
Ru ^{III} catalysed oxidations in the absence of Cl ⁻						
[CAT]	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	—
[AA]	0.86	0.46	0.31	0.52	0.40	—
[H ⁺]	-0.90	-0.70	-0.83	-0.86	-0.73	—
[Ru ^{III}]	0.28	0.45	0.34	0.41	0.38	—
Uncatalysed oxidations in the absence of Cl ⁻						
[CAT]	2.0	2.0	2.0	—	2.0	—
[AA]	1.0	1.0	1.0	—	1.0	—
[H ⁺]	-1.0	-1.0	-1.0	—	-1.0	—

were linear with negative fractional slopes, indicating inverse fractional order dependence of rate on [H⁺], in all the cases (Table 3). The rates increased with increase in [AA]₀ with fractional order kinetics in [AA], contrary to first order kinetics generally observed in the uncatalysed oxidations (Table 3). The plots of k_{obs} vs [AA] were linear (Figs. 1–3) with all the amino acids. The rates also increased with increase in [Ru^{III}] and [Cl⁻] with fractional order kinetics in both [Ru^{III}] and [Cl⁻] for all the oxidations (Table 3). The plots of k_{obs} vs [Ru^{III}] were linear with finite intercepts on the ordinates (Fig. 4). Addition of either the reduced product of the oxidant (TSA) or variation in ionic strength of the medium had no significant effect on the rates of oxidation (Table 2). Decrease in dielectric constant of the medium by changing the solvent composition

Fig. 1. Plots of k_{obs} vs [AA], (Gly, Ala); [CAT]₀ = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³; [HClO₄] = 3.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³; [Cl⁻] = 1.0 × 10⁻¹ mol dm⁻³; [Ru^{III}] = 4.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³; Temp. = 303 K.

with methanol decreased the rates and the plots of log k_{obs} vs 1/D were linear with negative slopes (Fig. 5).

The rates were measured at different temperatures at varying [AA]. Coefficients of the rate-controlling steps have been calculated at each temperature as described under discussion. The latter constants were used to compute the activation parameters (Table 4).

TABLE 4—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS ASSOCIATED WITH RATE-LIMITING STEPS REPRESENTED BY COEFFICIENTS k AND k'

	Gly	Ala	Val	Leu	Phe	Ser
	From k'' values		From k values			
E _a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	52.0	51.4	56.5	52.2	56.9	54.1
log A	5.8	8.58	9.67	8.99	9.63	9.18
ΔH [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	51.7	50.3	51.4	51.4	56.4	52.1
ΔS [‡] (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-88.2	-33.5	-28.1	-28.1	-34.8	-28.1
ΔG [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	78.5	61.5	60.0	60.0	60.9	60.6
	From k ₀ values		From k' values			
E _a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	41.9	51.2	47.0	67.6	24.2	43.9
log A	4.01	8.89	8.04	11.6	3.6	7.34
ΔH [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	39.11	50.8	42.2	56.0	21.9	42.8
ΔS [‡] (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-129.17	-31.6	-59.5	+19.9	-125.4	-58.8
ΔG [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	78.4	61.5	60.8	60.0	59.9	60.6

*Vide equations (14) and (15) and related text.

Fig 2. Plots of k_{obs} vs $[AA]$ (Val, Leu), $[CAT]_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[HClO_4] = 3.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Cl^-] = 1.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Ru^{III}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp = 303 K

Fig 4 Plots of (A) k_{obs} vs $1/[H^+]$; $10^5 [CAT]_0 = 50 [AA]_0 = 10 [Cl^-] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Ru^{III}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp = 303 K: (a) Ala, (b) Val, (c) Leu, (d) Phe and (e) Ser; (B) k_{obs} vs $[Ru^{III}]$; $10^5 [CAT]_0 = 50 [AA]_0 = 33.33 [HClO_4] = 10 [Cl^-] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp = 303 K: (a) Ala, (b) Val, (c) Phe, (d) Leu and (e) Ser.

Fig 3 Plots of k_{obs} vs $[AA]$ (Phe, Ser), $[CAT]_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[HClO_4] = 3.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Cl^-] = 1.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Ru^{III}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp = 303 K

In acid solutions, amino acids exist in the following protonation equilibrium,

where, R is an alkyl or aryl moiety as indicated earlier. Chloramine-T ($ArSO_2NCIna$) is fairly a strong electrolyte in aqueous solution. Depending upon pH of the medium it furnishes different types of oxidising species⁶. The following equilibria exist in its aqueous solutions.

Fig 5 Plots of (A) $\log k_{obs}$ vs % methanol, $10^4[\text{CAT}]_0 = 50$, $[\text{AA}]_0 = 33.33$, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 10$, $[\text{Cl}^-] = 1.0$ mol dm^{-3} , $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm^{-3} ; (B) ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger .

Therefore, the probable reactive species in acid solutions of CAT are ArSO_2NHCl , $\text{ArSO}_2\text{NCl}_2$, HOCl , $\text{ArSO}_2\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}^+$, H_2OCl^+ and Cl_2 or a loose complex in the presence of chloride ion.

Mechanisms of oxidation: The kinetics of second order in $[\text{CAT}]$, fractional orders each in $[\text{AA}]$, $[\text{Cl}^-]$ and $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ and inverse fractional order in $[\text{H}^+]$ (Table 3) generally observed for the oxidations of amino acids and non-influence of the added reduced product of the oxidant or variation in ionic strength of the medium on the rates of oxidations can be accounted by two-pathway mechanism (Schemes 1 and 2).

Scheme 1

The rate law (10) is in accordance with Scheme 1.

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} &= K_2 K_3 k_4 [\text{CAT}]^2 [\text{Cl}^-] [\text{S}] \\ &= \frac{K_1 K_2 K_3 k_4 [\text{CAT}]^2 [\text{Cl}^-] [\text{SH}^+]}{[\text{H}^+]} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Scheme 2

The rate law (11) is in conformity with Scheme 2,

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = K_5 k_6 [\text{CAT}]^2 [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] \quad (11)$$

The following combined rate laws account for the observed results,

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 K_2 K_3 k_4 [\text{CAT}]^2 [\text{SH}^+] [\text{Cl}^-]}{[\text{H}^+]} + K_5 k_6 [\text{CAT}]^2 [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] \quad (12)$$

or

$$k_{obs} = \frac{K_1 K_2 K_3 k_4 [\text{SH}^+] [\text{Cl}^-]}{[\text{H}^+]} + K_5 k_6 [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] \quad (13)$$

The rate law (13) predicts linearities between k_{obs} and $[\text{AA}]$, k_{obs} and $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$, and k_{obs} and $1/[\text{H}^+]$. As already indicated, the plots of k_{obs} vs $[\text{AA}]$ (Figs. 1-3), k_{obs} vs $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ and k_{obs} vs $1/[\text{H}^+]$ (Fig. 4) were linear in conformity with the predictions, thus providing support to the suggested mechanisms.

At constant $[\text{Cl}^-]$, the rate law (13) may be written as

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k[\text{SH}^+]}{[\text{H}^+]} + k'[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] \quad (14)$$

where, $k = K_1 K_2 K_3 k_4 [\text{Cl}^-]$ and $k' = K_5 k_6$ (15)

The constants k and k' were calculated from the above plots. Further, the constants computed from the plots of k_{obs} vs $[\text{AA}]$ were employed to predict the rate constants from the rate law (14) as $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ varied and vice versa. The predicted values compared with the experimental constants are shown in Tables 5-7. As can be seen there is good agreement between the predicted and experimental constants.

$[\text{AA}]$ were varied at different temperatures and the constants k and k' were calculated at each temperature. The latter constants were used to compute two sets of activation parameters from the plots of $\log k$ vs $1/T$, $\log (k/T)$ vs $1/T$, $\log k'$ vs $1/T$ and $\log (k'/T)$ vs $1/T$ (Table 4).

Glycine, the parent amino acid is an exception to the above behaviour. The rate showed first order kinetics in $[\text{CAT}]$, fractional orders each in $[\text{Cl}^-]$ and $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$, and an inverse fractional order in

TABLE 5—COMPARISON OF PREDICTED AND EXPERIMENTAL RATE CONSTANTS FOR Ru^{III} CATALYSED OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS (AA) BY CHLORAMINE-T (CAT) IN PRESENCE OF CHLORIDE ION AT DIFFERENT [H⁺]

[H ⁺] × 10 ² mol dm ⁻³	<i>k</i> _{obs} (× 10 dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)									
	Ala		Val		Leu		Phe		Ser	
	Pred.	Expt.	Pred.	Expt.	Pred.	Expt.	Pred.	Expt.	Pred.	Expt.
	Predicted using constants computed from the plot of <i>k</i> _{obs} vs [Ru ^{III}]									
1.0	14.2	13.8	20.9	19.0	25.3	23.8	18.0	23.8	20.2	18.2
2.0	7.6	7.6	11.6	11.3	13.4	14.4	9.5	10.0	10.7	9.8
3.0	5.4	5.3	8.6	8.6	9.5	9.8	6.6	6.6	7.5	7.4
5.0	3.7	3.9	6.0	6.0	6.2	6.4	4.4	4.4	5.1	5.4
	Predicted using constants computed from plot of <i>k</i> _{obs} vs [AA]									
1.0	12.5	13.8	19.5	19.0	23.1	23.8	14.6	23.8	14.2	18.2
2.0	7.3	7.6	11.3	11.3	13.1	14.4	8.7	10.0	9.1	9.8
3.0	5.6	5.3	8.6	8.6	9.8	9.8	6.7	6.6	7.4	7.4
5.0	4.2	3.9	6.3	6.0	6.8	6.4	5.3	4.4	6.0	5.4

TABLE 6—COMPARISON OF PREDICTED AND EXPERIMENTAL RATE CONSTANTS FOR Ru^{III} CATALYSED OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS (AA) BY CHLORAMINE-T (CAT) IN PRESENCE OF CHLORIDE ION AT DIFFERENT [Ru^{III}]

[Ru ^{III}] × 10 ⁵ mol dm ⁻³	<i>k</i> _{obs} (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)									
	Ala		Val		Leu		Phe		Ser	
	Pred.	Expt.	Pred.	Expt.	Pred.	Expt.	Pred.	Expt.	Pred.	Expt.
	Predicted using constants computed from plot <i>k</i> _{obs} vs [AA]									
4.0	5.3	5.3	8.6	8.6	9.8	9.8	6.6	6.6	7.4	7.4
8.0	7.3	6.9	11.7	11.2	13.0	11.5	9.5	7.8	11.3	8.9
12.0	9.3	7.6	14.8	12.9	16.0	12.9	12.4	8.7	15.3	10.2
16.0	11.3	8.5	17.9	15.5	19.2	14.1	15.4	9.6	19.3	11.2
	Predicted using constants computed from plot <i>k</i> _{obs} vs 1/[H ⁺]									
4.0	5.3	5.3	8.6	8.6	9.6	9.8	6.9	6.6	7.3	7.4
8.0	6.6	6.9	12.1	11.2	12.0	11.3	7.8	7.8	9.2	8.9
12.0	7.8	7.6	15.6	12.9	14.5	12.9	8.6	8.7	11.1	10.2
16.0	9.1	8.5	19.1	15.5	17.0	13.1	9.4	9.6	13.0	14.1

TABLE 7—COMPARISON OF PREDICTED AND EXPERIMENTAL RATE CONSTANTS FOR Ru^{III} CATALYSED OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS (AA) BY CHLORAMINE-T (CAT) IN PRESENCE OF CHLORIDE ION AS [AA] ARE VARIED

[AA] × 10 ² mol dm ⁻³	<i>k</i> _{obs} (× 10 dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)									
	Ala		Val		Leu		Phe		Ser	
	Pred.	Expt.	Pred.	Expt.	Pred.	Expt.	Pred.	Expt.	Pred.	Expt.
	Predicted using constants computed from plot <i>k</i> _{obs} vs [Ru ^{III}]									
1.0	3.2	3.8	5.4	5.9	5.7	6.0	3.8	4.8	4.4	5.6
2.0	5.3	5.3	8.5	8.6	9.8	9.8	6.6	6.6	7.4	7.4
5.0	11.7	10.8	17.8	17.4	22.4	20.5	15.2	12.4	16.7	12.8
10.0	22.3	19.2	33.3	31.3	43.4	37.8	29.5	21.8	32.1	20.6
	Predicted using constants computed from plot <i>k</i> _{obs} vs 1/[H ⁺]									
1.0	3.3	3.8	6.0	5.9	6.0	6.0	3.9	4.8	4.6	5.6
2.0	5.3	5.3	8.6	8.6	9.6	9.8	6.9	6.6	7.3	7.4
5.0	11.6	10.8	16.3	17.4	20.0	20.5	16.1	12.4	15.5	12.8
10.0	21.9	19.2	29.0	31.3	37.7	37.8	31.5	21.8	29.1	20.6

[H⁺]. The rate decreased with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium. Addition of either the reduced product of the oxidant or variation in ionic strength of the medium had no significant effect on the rate of oxidation. These results may be explained by Schemes 3 and 4.

The combined rate law (16) accounts for the observed results for the oxidation of Gly,

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 K_2 k_7 [\text{CAT}][\text{Cl}^-][\text{SH}^+]}{[\text{H}^+]} + k_8 [\text{CAT}][\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] \quad (16)$$

or

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_1 K_2 k_7 [\text{Cl}^-] [\text{SH}^+]}{[\text{H}^+]} + k_8 [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] \quad (17)$$

or

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k'' [\text{SH}^+]}{[\text{H}^+]} + k_8 [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] \quad (18)$$

where, $k'' = K_1 K_2 k_7 [\text{Cl}^-]$ at constant $[\text{Cl}^-]$. The constants k'' and k_8 were calculated from the plots of k_{obs} vs $[\text{Gly}]$, $1/[\text{H}^+]$ or $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ (Fig. 1).⁶

Further, the constants computed from one plot were used to predict the rate constants from the rate law (18) as the other two were varied and vice versa. There was reasonable agreement between the predicted values and the experimental rate constants testing the consistency of the rate law (18), deduced based on suggested mechanisms. $[\text{Gly}]$ was varied at different temperatures (Fig. 1) and the constants k'' and k_8 have been calculated at each temperature. The latter values were used to compute two sets of activation parameters (Table 4).

A typical detailed mechanism of oxidation of amino acids by chloramine-T under these conditions is similar to the one reported elsewhere².

Solvent effects on the rates of ion-ion, ion-dipolar molecule and dipolar molecule-dipolar molecule reactions have been discussed elsewhere^{6,7}. For the limiting case of zero angle of approach between two dipoles or an ion-dipole system, Amis⁶ showed that a plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/D$ gives a straight line with a negative slope for a reaction between a negative ion and a dipole or two dipoles. The present observations are in conformity with these predictions (Fig. 5). The observed non-dependence of rate on the ionic strength of the medium is also in conformity with the proposed mechanisms.

Negative values of entropy of activation indicate that more ordered activated complexes are formed

due to decrease in the number of degrees of freedom. Almost the same values for free energies of activation show that similar mechanisms operate for all the oxidations. Further, the plot of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger is linear (Fig. 5) with an isokinetic temperature of about 377 K. The latter is higher than the temperature range employed in the present investigations, indicating that the reactions are enthalpy-controlled.

Comparison of kinetic data for the Ru^{III} catalysed oxidation of amino acids by chloramine-T both in the presence and absence of chloride ion with those for the uncatalysed oxidations reveals the significant role of Ru^{III} in the oxidative decarboxylation of amino acids. Ru^{III} not only enhances the rates of oxidations but also significantly alters the kinetics in $[\text{AA}]$ and $[\text{H}^+]$. It provides an alternative amino acid independent path for the oxidations.

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